

EDUCATION**AWARENESS OF PARENTS TOWARDS DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN****Mr. Metakari U. V.***Assistant Professor,
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Today, however, more often than not, Mom is out working. Not only is mother out of the house and away from her young child but in more and more cases, one of the parents-usually the father-is missing completely. In addition to the increasing numbers of single-parent families, there are families formed through remarriages, resulting in six million children living with step-parents. What are the implications of all these statistics for parents and teachers of today? In what ways does the changing family, scene affect us and how are we expected, to deal with these changes?

Obviously, today's parent has a much more complex task of raising a young child. Most young people no longer have an extended family of grandparents, cousins, brothers and sisters, and parents to rely on for baby-sitting and just plain old commonsense advice. The mother or father now has to make important decisions about teaching values and reinforcing them all alone. Certainly there are books and resources organizations, but those aren't (like) same as a caring relative. Many of today's parental anxieties stem from this feeling of being alone and being overwhelmed with responsibility for making decisions. Our institutions seem to be of little help, the school and the larger society seem to be in conflict as to what is good and bad. There are no clear-cut models of what a child should grow up to be like at least none that everyone agrees on and supports consistently.

INTRODUCTION:

Our families and schools have undergone more changes in the last decade than in fifty years of our grandparents' time. Today, our roles are no longer as clearly defined.

When our parents were young, there were usually mere family members in the home to teach children "how to behave". For example, in the 1920s more than half the households had at least one other adult-grandparent, aunt, uncle-besides the two parents. In the 1950s that figure

dropped to 10 percent, and today it is about 4 percent. That means most of the teaching of values and "proper behaviour" rests with Mom and Dad.

When a mother or father has to spend most of his or her waking hours working to earn enough to pay for just the basic needs of a family, there is little time or energy left to spend with children. Many families no longer sit down to eat together or share in family project or simply converse. Parents rely on television to baby-sit their children, and the children themselves have gotten into the habit of sitting impassively in front of the TV and tuning out anything the rest of the family may have to communicate. In a very real sense, parents are being pushed out of the traditional family roles by social and economic forces beyond their control

With so many forces working against the nuclear¹ family, it is no wonder that child abuse, family abandonment, suicide and delinquency are on the rise.

The following diagram explains the importance of home learning in the development of a child

What Can Parents Do?

- 1) Offer whatever help you can to the school. It is the thought which counts and many schools, especially the smaller ones, are perpetually short of money. Discarded, toys and books, money for schools fund, dressing-lip clothes, magazines, games, flowers for assembly; these can lead the way to such things as accompanying school outings giving talks at the schools, organizing jumble sales or fetes.
- 2) Join the PTA or Parent's Association. Take more active part if you are already a member; try to help form at if there isn't one.

- 3) Write or telephone your thanks if your child is getting on well or is being given extra facilities, such as Saturday morning football school journey, educational excursions. Make it clear that you appreciate this voluntary work. Ask if you can help with it in any way.
- 4) Reply to school reports. Ask for clarification if necessary; give your view of your child. If you feel grateful say so! Say what kind of report would like.
- 5) Ask to see the head or class teacher. Do this if you feel it will help the school and the child. Find out how you can help your child at home. Do not make him afraid to invite the head or the teacher for a talk at your home - he can only say 'no'! Attend school functions whenever you can.
- 6) Remember the teacher's point of view; your child may be a very different personality at school.
 - a) Parent-teacher co-operation should not make life more difficult for teachers; this may largely depend on you, the parent.
 - b) Do not grumble about school in front of children.
 - c) The teachers are struggling against enormous difficulties-overlarge classes, out-of-date building, and inadequate facilities. Make it clear that you know this and are trying to do something about it, by letters to the press, through your Trade Union or political party etc.
- 7) Lastly, do not just worry or grouse about your child at school. Act; ask for information and advise other parents to do the same.

From the above information it becomes clear that parents should play a key role in the development of their children for becoming them responsible citizens of our nation.

However, due to changing nature of our family structure (from joint families to nuclear families) and change in status of both mother and father (housewife to working women), the involvement of parents in children's development seems to be decreasing day by day. Parents today are ready to give money in more than sufficient quantity but time is less quantity & also in quality.

This change, certainly, influences on the development of our young generation

OBJECTIVES:-

- 1) To study the opinions of children about their parents & opinions of parents about the development of their children.
- 2) To study the parents awareness about the physical development of the children.

- 3) To study the parents awareness about intellectual development of the children.
- 4) To study the parents awareness about emotional development of the children.
- 5) To the study the parents awareness about social development of the children.

DATA BASED METHODOLOGY:-

The researcher has selected the survey method.

The researchers selected one area of Kolhapur city which is of educated & working families. They visited 37 families & interviewed 37 parents & 72 children (age group yrs. 0 to 14) using separate questionnaires for parents & children.

DATA ANALYSIS:-

PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT

**Table No. 1 A) Opinions of Children
Analysis of questions related to physical development.**

Que. No.	Points of Question	Response	Percentage
1	Regular Exercise	19	51.35%
2	Medical Checkup in school	26	70.27%
3	Diet	22	59.45%
4	Sex Education	16	43.24%

Observation:

- 1) Majority (70%) children give emphasis on their own medical checkup programme conducted in school.
- 2) Almost 50% of children are attentive towards.
- 3) Awareness about sex education is below 50%.

Table No. 2 B) Opinions of Parents

Que. No.	Points of Question.	Response	Percentage
1	Care after delivery	21	56.75%
2	Medical advice regarding child growth	16	43.24%
3	Development of child	19	51.35%
4	Provision of Games & Sports to Children	22	59.46%
5	Rest	15	40.54%
6	Sex Education	10	27.02%

Observation: 1) Almost; 60% of parents are aware about provision of sports & games to their children, but awareness about provision of rest is low. (40%).

2) 50% of parents aware about their children's growth, but very few (27%) are found ready to give sex education to their children.

3) Almost 56% mother-parents have taken purposeful care after delivery.

INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT

Table No. 3 A) Opinions of children

Que. No.	Points of Question	Response	Percentage
1	Reading	27	72.37%
2	Entertainment/Recreation	19	51.35%
3	Study habits	31	83.78%
4	Schooling	28	75.68%
5	Role of parents regarding intellectual development	29	78.38%

Observation:

1. Majority of children (72% to 83%) are satisfactory⁷ about their intellectual development,
2. 50% of children are found to treat recreating activities as supporting activities for intellectual development.

Table No. 4 D) opinions of Parents

Que. No.	Points of Question	Response	Percentage
1	Development of brain & mental abilities	26	29.73%
2	Facts of acquiring information	31	83.78%
3	Awareness about physical disabilities	28	75.66%
4	Learning atmosphere	14	37.84%

Observation :

1. Very few parents have knowledge about development processes of brain & mental abilities of human being.
2. Almost all (75%-84%) parents are aware about facts of information and also about physical disabilities of their children.
3. Parents in very small proportion are aware about providing learning opportunities to their children.

EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Table No. 5 A) Opinions of children

Que. No.	Points of Question	Response	Percentage
1	Relationship with family member	27	72.97%
2	Praising atmosphere	26	70.27%
3	Differential treatment in development	21	56.75%
4	Caring by parents	18	56.75%

Observation:

1. Majority of children (72 %) were satisfactory about their family relationship and atmosphere in their homes.
2. 50% of children agreed about differential treatment to boy-child & girl-child in their homes.
3. Only 50% children were happy about care taken by their parents.

Table No. 6 D) Opinions of Parents

Que. No.	Points of Question	Response	Percentage
1	Fear	24	64.86%
2	Anger	30	81.08%
3	Aggressiveness	25	67.56%
4	Relationship with Children	29	78.38%
5	Guidance	31	83.78%

Observation:

1. Majority of the parents use fear anger in daily life for growing up their Children.
2. Almost all parents provide guidance for developing the emotions to their children.

SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

Table No. 7 D) Opinions of Parents

Que. No.	Points of Question	Response	Percentage
1	Loneliness	30	19.02%
2	Friendship	32	86.48%
3	Participation in teams	26	70.27%
4	Relationship with Guest & Teacher	34	91.89%

Observation:

1. Almost all the children were satisfactory about their social development.

Table No. 8 D) Opinions of Parents

Que. No.	Points of Question	Response	Percentage
1	Restrictions on Girl child	16	43.24%
2	Training for friendship	21	56.75%
3	Development of social competence's	24	64.86%

Observation:

1. Nearly 50% of parents were found to provide purposeful guidance for social development of their children.

FINDINGS:

1. The following major findings can be drawn from this study. 1. Awareness about balanced food, importance of rest & exercise among parents and children was only 50%.
2. Parents found neutral about providing sex education to their children.
3. Children were found to be satisfactory regarding their intellectual development; however parents were not aware about brain development, relation between diet, exercise & brain development.
4. Parents were found to ready to acquire information, but were unable to prepare learning atmosphere at home.
5. Majority of the students found satisfactory the family relation in their homes for their emotional development. However, majority of the parents use fear & anger which may affect (he emotional status of the children.
6. 50% children agreed that there is difference between treatment to girl & boy in their homes; by their parents.
7. Almost all children were found satisfactory with their social development; however 50% of parent was not providing appropriate guidance for social development of their children.

CONCLUSION:

This is the picture of involvement of parents in developing their children. These parents are educated and working in sophisticated way and from middle & higher class from a city. However; the proportion of general awareness about child's development is nearly 50% so what about the rural , uneducated parents? If we want a developed country in 2020 a detailed survey about parent education is necessary.

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